

✦ Aahar in Ayurveda: Millets as a Pathya in Life style disorders; A Comprehensive review from Bhavpraksh Nighantu

PRESENTATION BY,

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Introduction

- The whole world is celebrating the ‘International Year of Millets’, as declared by the United Nations in 2023.
- **India is the largest producer of millets** in the world
- Evidence of millet usage in India dates back to the **Vedic period**. However, in recent years, due to various reasons, millets were **sidelined** from the main course and replaced by **wheat and rice**.
- Currently, due to **faulty lifestyle habits, lifestyle disorders** are on the rise.

Conti..

- **Lifestyle disorders** include heart diseases, obesity, type-2 diabetes, hypertension, dyslipidemia, and conditions associated with smoking and alcohol consumption, among others.
- These are classified as **non-communicable diseases (NCDs)**, and as per research data, they account for **around 40 million deaths annually**, i.e., nearly **70%** of global mortality.
- In Ayurvedic context, these disorders are comparable to **Santarpanajanya Vyadhi** (diseases caused by over-nourishment). [Charaka Samhita, Sutrasthana 23/5]

Conti..

- By applying Ayurvedic principles, these conditions can be prevented, managed, or even reversed.
- Ayurveda has always emphasized **Ahara (diet)** and **Vihara (lifestyle)**, especially through the lens of **Pathya–Apathya (wholesome vs. unwholesome practices)**.
- The classical texts of Ayurveda are rich with **solutions for lifestyle disorders**, with a strong emphasis on the consumption of **Pathya Aahara - and millets**, with their inherent properties, fit well within this concept.

Role of Millets in Modern Lifestyle Disorders

- Today's life is very fast-paced, and most people prefer **fast food**, which often leads to **malnourishment**.
- Malnourishment can occur due to either **overnourishment (Santarpana)** or **undernourishment (Apatarpana)**.
- The use of **millets**, an ancient and nutritious grain-like seed, in our daily diet provides **numerous health benefits**.
- Including millets in the diet while avoiding **refined and processed foods** (such as packed snacks, refined oils, and ready-to-eat meals) can help promote a **healthy lifestyle**.
- **Millets are particularly beneficial** in managing **Santarpanajanya Vikaras** (disorders due to overnutrition) and **Kapha-Pittaja Vikaras**, which are often linked to modern **non-communicable diseases (NCDs)** resulting from a **sedentary and sophisticated lifestyle**.

Material & Method:

- Different **Ayurvedic classics** have mentioned millets under the category of **Kshudra Dhanya**, and praised their properties.
- This presentation primarily focuses on **Bhavaprakasha Nighantu**, one of the most reputed and widely accepted Ayurvedic texts.
- In Bhavaprakasha Nighantu, millets are classified under **Dhanya Varga as Truna Dhanya**. Their properties (Guna), actions (Karma), and indications (Prayojana) are described in detail.
- *The **Dhanya Varga of Bhavaprakasha Nighantu** was studied and analyzed to compile data regarding the use of **millets in lifestyle disorders**.*
- Recent scientific research and citations from reputed journals and books were also incorporated.
- The data was **critically reviewed, comprehended systematically, and then presented in this paper.**

Aims and objectives

- To understand the concept of **Nidana Parivarjana** (eliminating causative factors) and **Prakriti Vighata** (counteracting disease pathology) in the context of **Santarpanjanya Vyadhi** through the use of millets.
- To explore the **role of millets** in managing and preventing **lifestyle disorders**, as described in **Ayurvedic texts and modern nutritional science**.
- To analyze the **properties, actions, and therapeutic indications of millets** as described in **Bhavaprakasha Nighantu (Dhanya Varga – Truna Dhanya)** and correlate them with their **clinical utility in current health challenges**.

Results & observation

In Bhavaprakasha Nighantu, under Dhanya Varga, millets are described under the group Kshudra Dhanya / Truna Dhanya.

Synonyms

क्षुद्रधान्य, कुधन्यम, तृणधान्य

Rasa - कषाय मधुर

Guna- लघु

Virya- उष्ण

Vipaka- कटु

Karma- लेखनम, क्लेदशोषकम, बद्धवितकं

Doshakarma- वातकर, पित्त रक्त कफपहाम

General
properties

यावनाल

Barley

कडगु

Foxtail

चीनाक

Porro

श्यामाक

Barnyard

नीवार

क्षुद्र धान्य

Khod

कोद्रव

अद्लय

गवेधुक

Safflower

कुसुम्भबीज

Bamboo

वंशयव

चारुक

Table

Sr.No.	Dravya	Scientific name	Family	dosha	Properties
1.	कडगु	<i>Setariaitalica</i> Beauv	Gramineae	वातकृद, श्लेष्महरा	भग्नसन्धान, वाजजनां, बृहणं गुरु ,रूक्षा,
2.	चीनाक	<i>Panicummiliaceum</i> Linn	Gramineae	वातकृद, श्लेष्महरा	सगशलक्षणुः
3.	श्यामाक (तृणबीजोत्तम)	<i>Echinochloa frumentacea</i>	Gramineae	वातलुः कफजित्तहत	शोषणो सगकगमारो, रूक्षो
4.	कोद्रव	<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> Linn.	Gramineae	जित्तकफिाहुः वातलो	ग्राही, जहमुः
5.	चारुक	<i>Saccharummunja</i> Roxb	Gramineae	रक्तजित्तक फिाहुः वातकिोनुः	वृष्यश्च, शीतलो लघग रूक्षो

Table

Sr.No.	Dravya	Scientific name	Family	dosha	Properties
6	वंशयव	Bambūsaarundinacea Will d	Gramineae	कफघ्नाश्च वातजित्करुः	रूक्षुः, सर बद्धमू तुः वृष्या
7.	कुसुम्भाबीज	Carthamustinctorius. Linn	Gramineae	रक्तजित्तक फिहा, Sजनलियाहा	
8	गवेधुक	Coixlachrymajobi Linn	Gramineae	त्कफनाजशनी	काश्यय कटगका स्वाद्वी
9.	नीवार	Hygroryzaaristata Nees	Gramineae	जित्तघ्नुः कफवातकृत	शीतलो, ग्राही
10.	यावनाल	-Sorghum vulgare Linn.	Gramineae	श्लेष्मजित्तजज त,	जहमुः, रूक्षुः, लघुगुः अवृष्य, क्लेदकृत्कजितो,

Discussion Santarpan vyadhi Nidana

- सन्तर्पयति यः
 - स्निग्धै
 - र्मधुरै
 - र्गुरु
 - पिच्छिलै
 - नवान्नै
 - र्नवमद्यैश्च
 - मांसैश्चानूपवारिजैः
 - गोरसै
 - गौडिकैश्चान्नैः
 - पैष्टिकैश्चातिमात्रशः
 - चेष्टाद्वेषी
 - दिवास्वप्न
 - शय्यासनसुखे रत
 - रोगास्तस्योपजायन्ते सन्तर्पणनिमित्तजाः | ५ |
- The cause of santarpan vyadhi (lifestyle disorders) are guru, sheeta, kledakar, avrushya, kaphavardhaka, pichilla, snigdha, Amavardhaka, Agnimandakar, bruhanitya and more.
 - **To counteract the cause guna of kshudradhanya is given**
 - General properties of millets are lekhanitya, kledashoshaka, laghu, ushna, vrushya, ruksha, grahi, karshyakar, laghu, rakhta, pitta, kaphashamaka.

ONE CAN UNDERSTAND IMPORTANT OF MILLETS BY
ACHARYA CHARAK MENTIONED IN ASHTANINDHTA
ATISTHALUYA CHIKISTA.

प्रशातिका प्रियङ्गुश्च श्यामाका यवका यवाः |
जूर्णाह्वाः कोद्रवा मुद्गाः कुलत्थाश्चक्रमुद्गकाः ||२५||
आढकीनां च बीजानि पटोलामलकैः सह |
भोजनार्थं प्रयोज्यानि पानं चानु मधूदकम् ||२६||

Modern researches have also proved that millets aids in hypolipidaemic, hypoglycemic etc too. Trina dhanya (Millets), They possess guna like Ruksha, Laghu, Kaphahara, Medohara, shoshan etc. with minimal proportion of them.

**According to several epidemiological research, regularly consuming millet grains and their byproducts is associated -
with a reduced risk for chronic diseases like diabetes, heart disease, cancer, and all-cause death**

CONCLUSION

- सन्तर्पणजन्य विकाराः arise due to guru, snigdha, madhura, kapha-pittavardhaka ahara and sedentary lifestyle.
- **Millets** are लघु, रुक्ष, लेखनीय, कफ-पित्त शामक – hence ideal for Santarpanajanya Vikaras.
- **Millets** are rich in dietary fiber, polyphenols, antioxidants, and micronutrients, supporting metabolism and gut health.
- Regular millet use helps manage **obesity, diabetes, metabolic syndrome, PCOS, and cardiovascular disorders.**
- **Environmentally sustainable** – they require less water, mature faster, and are pest-resistant, easing farmer burden.

Conti..

- Ayurveda and modern science both recognize millets as **functional food** for preventive and therapeutic health.
- Millets support **digestive fire (Agni)**, reduce Ama formation, and thus prevent many NCDs.
- Public awareness and Vaidya involvement can help **revive millet usage**, supporting both national health and economy.
- Thus, millets are not just food—they are a **path to Swasthya (health), Swasthya Rakshanam (prevention), and Aarogya Lakshya (public wellness)**.

Reference

- International Journal of Collaborative Research on Internal Medicine & Public Health: lifestyle disorder
- International Journal of Collaborative Research on Internal Medicine & Public Health: lifestyle disorder
- Acharya Yadavaji Trikamji, editor, (2nd ed.) Charak Samhita of Agnivesha, Sutra Sthana; Santarpaniya Adhyaya: chapter 23, verse-4,5, Varanasi: Chaukhamba Orientalia, 2014; 122
- Acharya Yadavaji Trikamji, editor, (2nd ed.) Charak Samhita of Agnivesha, Vimansthana; Roganikviman Adhyaya: chapter 7, verse-14, Varanasi: Chaukhamba Orientalia, 2014; 258
- Late Dr. G.S. Pandey, editor, Prof. K. C. Chuneekar; commentor; Sri Bhavamishra, Bhavaprakasa Nighantu,; Dhanyavarga, chapter-8, verse-74, varanasi: chaukhambhaorientalia, 2010; 643
- Late Dr. G.S. Pandey, editor, Prof. K. C. Chuneekar; commentor; Sri Bhavamishra, Bhavaprakasa Nighantu,; Dhanyavarga, chapter-8, verse-74-75, varanasi: chaukhambhaorientalia, 2010; 643
- Late Dr. G.S. Pandey, editor, Prof. K. C. Chuneekar; commentor; Sri Bhavamishra, Bhavaprakasa Nighantu,; Dhanyavarga, chapter-8, verse-75, varanasi: chaukhambhaorientalia, 2010; 643
- Late Dr. G.S. Pandey, editor, Prof. K. C. Chuneekar; commentor; Sri Bhavamishra, Bhavaprakasa Nighantu,; Dhanyavarga, chapter-8, verse-76-77, varanasi: chaukhambhaorientalia, 2010; 643
- Late Dr. G.S. Pandey, editor, Prof. K. C. Chuneekar; commentor; Sri Bhavamishra, Bhavaprakasa Nighantu,; Dhanyavarga, chapter-8, verse-78, varanasi: chaukhambhaorientalia, 2010; 644
- Late Dr. G.S. Pandey, editor, Prof. K. C. Chuneekar; commentor; Sri Bhavamishra, Bhavaprakasa Nighantu,; Dhanyavarga, chapter-8, verse-79, varanasi: chaukhambhaorientalia, 2010; 645
- Late Dr. G.S. Pandey, editor, Prof. K. C. Chuneekar; commentor; Sri Bhavamishra, Bhavaprakasa Nighantu,; Dhanyavarga, chapter-8, verse-80, varanasi:

Thank You For Attention

"GIVE ME SIX HOURS
TO CHOP DOWN
A TREE & I WILL
SPEND THE FIRST
FOUR SHARPENING
THE AXE."

-ABRAHAM LINCOLN

